

Journal home page:
<http://www.iajpr.com/index.php/en/>

**INDO AMERICAN
 JOURNAL OF
 PHARMACEUTICAL
 RESEARCH**

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF TRANSDERMAL FILMS OF LERCANIDIPINE FROM ACRYLIC FILMS

S.Uma devi¹, Vaijyanthi.C.M^{*1}, Jiji jose², Iswarya karapareddy¹, Satheesh Kumar³, Noufal Majeed⁴, Swathi G Panikkar¹

¹ Department of pharmaceuticals, R V S College of pharmaceutical science, Sulur, Coimbatore, India.

² Department of pharmaceuticals, Malik dinar college of pharmacy, Kasargod, Kerala, India.

³ Department of pharmaceutical sciences, Vinayaka Mission College of pharmacy, Selam, India.

⁴ Department of pharmacology, Ultra college of pharmacy, Madurai, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 25 July 2012
 Available online 30 July 2012

Keywords

Lercanidipine, transdermal, plasticizer, permeation enhancers, eudragit RL 100

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research was to develop a matrix diffusion type transdermal therapeutic system containing drug Lercanidipine with a blend of eudragit RL 100 and eudragit RS 100 as polymer system by the solvent evaporation technique with PEG 400 as plasticizer. Glycerin was used as enhance the transdermal permeation of Lercanidipine. Eight formulations with varied concentration of polymers, plasticizers and permeation enhancers were done and optimization of the concentration of formulation components was performed. Formulated transdermal films were evaluated for various physicochemical parameters, in vitro release, and stability studies. Good uniformity of the drug content among the patches was observed for all the formulations which ranged from 94.75% to 98.42%. Formulation variables such as polymer ratio, concentration of plasticizer and permeation enhancers were found to influence the in vitro drug release behavior of the formulated patches. Increasing the concentration of eudragit RL 100 and plasticizer, the presence of permeation enhancers were found to increase the in vitro drug release of the formulated patches. The total amount of drug released from the films over 8 and 24 hours followed the order: 10% w/w Glycerin > 10% w/w PEG 400 > 5% w/w Glycerin > 5% w/w PEG 400. Based on the physicochemical and drug release characteristics, the eudragit films with polyethylene glycol 400 and glycerin are suitable to design matrix diffusion type transdermal system for Lercanidipine and the F8 formulation with eudragit RL 100 to eudragit RS100 ratio 1:1, 5% w/w glycerin as permeation enhancer and 5% w/w PEG 400 as plasticizer showed a thickness of 0.260mm and drug loading of 3.912mg/cm² was considered as the best formulation. The cumulative percentage amount of drug release from the F8 formulation film was found to be 38.381% at the end of 8 hours and 58.154% at the end of 24 hours. The films were found to be stable during the entire stability period of 60 days at 45°C.

Corresponding author

Vaijyanthi.C.M, M-Pharm, Department of pharmaceuticals, R V S College of pharmaceutical sciences, Sulur, Coimbatore-641402. E-Mail address- vaijyanthibpharm@gmail.com, Mobile No- 8129558295

INTRODUCTION

Transdermal therapeutic systems can be defined as self contained, discrete dosage forms which, when applied to the intact skin, delivers the drug through the skin at controlled rate to the systemic circulation. It is anticipated that transdermal drug delivery system can be designed to input drugs at appropriate rates to maintain suitable plasma-drug level for therapeutic efficacy, without the periodic into the plasma concentration that would accompany toxicity or lack of efficacy. Transdermal systems are ideally suited for diseases that demand chronic treatment such as cardiovascular diseases, which require prolonged medication, and sometimes lifelong therapy is advised. It also provides a controlled release of medicament in to patients. Lercanidipine is a calcium channel blocker and chemically known as 3,5-pyridinedicarboxylic acid, 1,4-dihydro-2,6-dimethyl-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-2-[(3,3-diphenylpropyl) methylamino]-1,1-dimethylethyl methyl ester (+) . The mechanism of action of Lercanidipine involves their interference with the calcium entry in to the myocardial and vascular smooth muscle thus decreasing the availability of intracellular calcium. Antianginal property of this drug is probably due to the improvement in the coronary blood flow and decrease in the oxygen demand of the heart due to reduction in systemic vascular resistance, and blood pressure. The aims of the present study were to prepare transdermal patches of Lercanidipine by using backing membrane and release liner. The purpose was to provide the delivery of the drug at a controlled rate across intact skin.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Lercanidipine was received as a gift samples from Orchid Healthcare Ltd. Chennai, India. Eudragit RL 100, Eudragit RS 100 were obtained from Evonik Roehm polymers, Mumbai, India. Other materials used in the analytical grade. Double-distilled water was throughout the study.

METHOD OF PREPARATION

Procedure

In trial batch F1 eudragit RL 100:RS100 1:2 without PEG 400 and Glycerine. In trial formulation F2 eudragit RL 100:RS100 1:1 without PEG 400 and Glycerine. In trial formulation F3 eudragit RL 100:RS100 2:1 without PEG 400 and Glycerine. In trial formulation F4 and F5 eudragit RL 100:RS100 1:1 with PEG 400. In trial formulation F6 and F7 eudragit RL 100:RS100 1:1 with Glycerin. In trial F8 eudragit RL 100:RS100 1:1 with

both PEG 400 and Glycerin. In all the trial formulations acetone was used as casting solvent. The trial batch formula was given in Table.No. 1

FORMULATION OF LERCANIDIPINE TRANSDERMAL FILMS

The solubility of polymer should match with solubility of drug so as to prepare the transparent medicated films. The solubility of polymer was checked. Eudragit RL 100 and Eudragit RS 100 were soluble in acetone. The solubility of Lercanidipine was checked in acetone. Considering solubility of drug and polymer acetone was selected as solvent. The TDDS was prepared by film casting method. The TDDS was composed of different concentration of Eudragit RL 100 and Eudragit RS 100, along with drug Lercanidipine, Plasticizer, Polyethylene glycol-400. All ingredients were dissolved in acetone. The casting solutions were prepared by dissolving weighed quantities of polymers in acetone. The drug, plasticizers and permeation enhancer were then added to the polymer solution and thoroughly mixed to form a homogeneous mixture. The volume was made up to 10 ml with acetone. Entrapped air bubbles were removed by applying vacuum. 5 ml of the casting solution was poured into glass moulds and dried at room temperature for 24 hours for solvent evaporation. The patches were removed by peeling and cut into square dims of 1 cm x 1 cm. These patches were kept in desiccators for further drying and wrapped in Aluminum foil, packed in self-sealing covers.

EVALUATION OF FILMS

1. Physical Appearance

All the transdermal patches were visually inspected for colour, flexibility, homogeneity and smoothness. The films were found to have uniformly white coloured with homogeneous appearance, having sufficient flexibility and smooth texture.

2. Weight Variation

A set of five patches of each batch were weighed on a digital balance and the mean value were calculated. The test was done to check the uniformity of weight.

3. Film Thickness

The thickness was measured at five different places on a single patch using a Screw gauge and the mean values were calculated.

4. Percent flatness:

The percent flatness was measured by cutting the film in to three strips from centre of the film. The strips were cut so that each should be 4 cm length and 0.5 cm breadth. Each strip

was put on the clean surface without applying any additional pressure and measured its length to nearest centimeter by digital vernier caliper.

5. Moisture content:

The film was weighed and kept in a desiccator containing calcium chloride at 40°C in a drier for at least 24 hr or more until it shows a constant weight and report in terms of percentage (by weight) moisture content.

6. Moisture uptake:

The films casted in plastic moulds were used for moisture uptake studies. A weighed film kept in glass chamber at 40°C for 24 hr was taken out and exposed to two different relative humidity of 75 % (saturated solution of sodium chloride) and 92% (saturated solution of ammonium hydrogen phosphate) in two different glass chamber, respectively at room temperature. Then the weights were measured periodically.

7. Drug Content Uniformity

The patch (1 cm²) was transferred in to a graduated glass stopper flask containing 10 ml of methanol. The flask was shaken for 4 hrs in a mechanical shaker. Then the solution was filtered and residue was washed with methanol. 5ml of the filtrate was made up to 100 ml with phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and the absorbance was measured at 256.8 nm using the placebo patch solution as blank and the drug content was calculated.

8. Folding Endurance

The folding endurance is expressed as the number of folds (number of times the film is folded at the same place) required to break the specimen or to develop visible cracks. This also gives an indication of brittleness of the film. A strip of 2 cm x 2 cm was subjected to folding endurance by folding the patch at the same place repeatedly several times until a visible crack was observed.

9. In vitro performance

In vitro drug release studies

In vitro drug release studies were carried out by using Keshery - Chein Diffusion cell with cellophane membrane.

Cellophane Membrane

The Cellophane membrane was soaked in 50 ml of glycerin at room temperature for 10 - 12 hours before the experiment and then cut in to pieces of 1 cm² area. Then the membrane was mounted between donor and receptor compartment of the diffusion cell.

In-vitro Diffusion Cell

The in vitro permeation of the drug was studied using a modified Keshery -Chein diffusion cell in laboratory (Figure 12). The cell consists of two compartments, the donor and the receptor compartment. The donor compartment was in contact with ambient conditions of atmosphere. The receptor compartment was in contact with a solution in the receptor compartment (50ml of phosphate buffer pH 7.4) and the contents were stirred by a rod-shaped magnetic bead driven by a magnetic stirrer.

Drug Diffusion Studies

One patch of 1 cm² was placed in the donor compartment of the diffusion cell. The temperature of receptor compartment was maintained at 37 ± 1° C. The receptor solution was stirred with a magnetic stirrer at 50 rpm throughout the experiment. The donor compartment was in contact with receptor solution (50ml of phosphate buffer pH 7.4) at ambient conditions of the environment. 5 ml sample of the receptor fluid were withdrawn at predetermined time intervals (1 hr, 2 hr, 4 hr, 6 hr, 8 hr and 24 hr) and replaced immediately with same volume of phosphate buffer pH 7.4. The samples were suitably diluted with phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (2ml sample to 10ml) and analyzed for drug content at 256.8 nm using UV - visible spectrophotometer.

10. ***In-vitro* drug release kinetic studies**

To analyze the *In-vitro* release data various kinetic models were used to describe the release kinetics. The zero order rate Equation no: 1 describes the systems where the drug release rate is independent of its concentration. The first order Equation no: (2) describe the release from the system where release rate is concentration dependent. Higuchi described the release of drugs from insoluble matrix as a square root of time dependent process based on the Fickian diffusion Equation no: (3). The Hixson-Crowell root law Equation no: (4) describes the release from the systems where there is a change in surface area and diameter of particles. The Koresmeyer-peppas Equation no: (5) describes the mode of release of drug from swellable matrices.

$$C = K_0t \text{ ----- (1)}$$

Where, K_0 is zero order rate constant expressed in units of concentration/time and t is the time.

$$\text{Log } C = \text{Log } C_0 - Kt/2.303 \text{ ----- (2)}$$

$$\text{Where, } C_0 \text{ is the initial concentration of drug and } K \text{ is first order rate constant.} = Kt^{1/2} - Q \text{ ----- (3)}$$

Where, K is the constant reflecting the design variables of the system.

$$Q_0^{1/3} - Q_t^{1/3} = K_{HCl} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Where, Q_t is the amount of drug released in time t , Q_0 is the initial amount of the drug and K_{HC} is the rate constant for Hixson-Crowell rate equation.

$$M_t/M = Kt^n \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Where, M_t/M is fraction of drug release at time t , K is constant incorporating the structural and geometrical characteristics of the drug/ polymer system, n is diffusion exponent related to the mechanism of the release.

11. Stability Studies

To any rational design and evaluation of dosage forms, the stability of the active component must be major criteria in determining the acceptance or rejection. Drugs instability is indicated by a change in the physical appearance such as color, odor, taste or texture of the formulation, whereas in other instances chemical changes may occur which are ascertained through chemical analysis. The stability studies of the formulated transdermal patches were carried out on selected films (F8) were wrapped in Aluminum foil, packed properly in a self sealing cover, stored in desiccator and kept in a hot air oven at a temperature of 450°C for 90 days The patches were characterized for drug content and other parameters at regular intervals (0, 30, 60 and 90 days).

Table. No .1 Trial Formulations

Ingredients	Formulation batches							
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Drug-polymer ratio	1:5	1:5	1:5	1:5	1:5	1:5	1:5	1:5
Eudragit RL: RS100	1:2	1:1	2:1	2:1	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1
Lercanidipine	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
PEG-400	---	---	---	50	100	---	---	50
Glycerin	---	---	---	---	---	50	100	50
Acetone	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Film appearance

The films are found to have uniformly white colored with homogeneous appearance.

2. Weight Variation:

Drug loaded films were tested for weight variation. The weight ranged of formulation between 96.1mg to 112.2mg is shown in Table. No.2

3. Film Thickness

The thickness of the patches varied from 0.196 to 0.266mm No significant difference in thickness is observed among each group of patches indicating that the patches are uniform throughout is shown in Table. No. 3

Table. No.2 Weight Variation

Formulation	Weight (mg)
F1	96.1 ± 1.308
F2	97.0 ± 3.081
F3	98.5 ± 1.000
F4	99.7 ± 1.401
F5	101.5 ± 0.931
F6	104.6 ± 1.0
F7	108.7 ± 0.819
F8	112.2 ± 0.361

Table. No. 3 Thickness Uniformity

Formulation	Thickness (mm)
F1	0.196 ± 0.017
F2	0.217 ± 0.021
F3	0.203 ± 0.011
F4	0.230 ± 0.027
F5	0.256 ± 0.005
F6	0.237 ± 0.007
F7	0.260 ± 0.008
F8	0.266 ± 0.005

Table.No.4. Moisture content

Formulation code	Moisture content
F1	2.18%
F2	2.95%
F3	3.43%
F4	3.62%
F5	3.89%
F6	4.12%
F7	4.23%
F8	5.01%

Table No.5 Moisture uptake

Formulation code	Relative humidity	
	75% RH	92% RH
F1	5.02	11.78
F2	5.28	11.99
F3	5.69	12.28
F4	5.93	12.49
F5	6.12	12.55
F6	6.45	12.89
F7	6.54	14.34
F8	6.65	14.68

Table.No.6 Drug content

Formulation code	Drug content
F1	95.41
F2	96.23
F3	98.42
F4	95.85
F5	96.27
F6	96.82
F7	94.75
F8	97.80

4. Moisture content:

The film was weighed and kept in a desiccator and was reported moisture content in terms of percentage (by weight) is 2.18% to 5.01%. The results are shown in table. No. 4

5. Moisture uptake:

The films was kept in glass chamber at 75 %(saturated solution of sodium chloride) is 5.02 to 6.65 and 92 %(saturated solution of ammonium hydrogen phosphate) is 11.78 to 14.68 respectively is shown in Table No.5

6. Drug Content

7. That there was no significant difference in the drug content among patches (Table. No 6) indicating the uniformity in drug content. Good uniformity of the drug content among the patches was observed for all the formulations which ranged from 94.75% to 98.42%. The result showed that the process employed to prepare the films in this study was capable of producing films with uniform drug content and minimum batch variability.

8. Folding Endurance

The Folding endurance of the films shows greater than 300. This indicates that as the concentration of polymer increased, there was increase in the folding endurance of the transdermal films.

Table.No. 7 In-Vitro Drug Release Study

Formulation Code	%o Drug Release						
	Initial	1hr	3hr	6hr	12hr	15hr	24hr
F1	0	4.183	7.730	16.352	20.935	37.525	45.485
F2	0	4.812	8.547	16.212	23.301	36.683	56.426
F3	0	5.004	9.167	17.830	22.901	39.727	56.995
F4	0	5.651	10.798	20.649	32.079	44.064	61.849
F5	0	7.115	12.243	23.993	32.771	42.091	60.686
F6	0	8.809	17.489	29.639	40.067	58.803	67.514
F7	0	10.474	21.195	34.235	48.763	62.285	75.296
F8	0	10.509	21.434	33.339	51.409	68.381	88.154

Table.No.8 Data Analysis for F8 Optimized Formulation

Sr. no	Time (hrs)	% drug release	Square root of time	Log time	cumulative % drug release	Log cumulative % drug release	% drug remaining	Log % drug remaining
1	1	10.51	1	0	10.51	1.021	77.644	1.890
2	2	21.434	1.414	0.301	31.944	1.504	66.72	1.824
3	3	33.34	1.732	0.477	65.284	1.814	54.814	1.738
4	6	51.41	2.449	0.778	116.694	2.067	36.744	1.565
5	9	68.38	3	0.954	185.074	2.267	19.774	1.296
6	12	88.154	3.464	1.079	273.228	2.436	0	0

Table No .9 Data Analysis Results for F9 Optimized Formulation

Batch	Zero order		first order		Higuchi		KorsmeyerPeppas	
	r^2	K_0 (mg/L/hr)	r^2	K_1 (h^{-1})	r^2	K_{Hg} (h^{-1})	r^2	N
F8	0.9717	7.842x	0.8183	-0.1488	0.9413	0.8584	0.9843	1.26x+1.097 + 2.2041

Table.No.10 Stability Studies of F8 Formulation:

Parameters	0 th day	1 Month	2 Month	3 Month
Weight uniformity	112.2	110.1	109.4	108.2
%Moisture content	5.01%	5.12%	5.32	5.35%
Drug content	97.80%	96.43%	95.89%	95.35%
Drug release	88.154	86.64%	85.34%	85.15%

9. In vitro drug release studies

In-vitro drug release studies were carried out through cellophane membrane to indicate the influence of polymer, plasticizer and permeation enhancer on the release of the drug. The Figure No.1 In-vitro Diffusion Cell

Figure No. 2 Weight Variation for All Formulations

Figure. No.3 Thickness Uniformity for All Formulations

Figure. No.4 Percentage Drug Release for F1-F4 Formulations

rate and amount drug release over 24 hrs were determined and results are summarized in Table.No.7. The cumulative percentage amount of drug released from F8 film was found to be 51.409 % at the end of 12 hours and 88.154% at the end of 24 hours. Comparatively, the F8 formulation shows good results.

Figure No.5 Percentage Drug Release for F5-F8 Formulations

Figure. No.6 Zero Order Kinetic Drug Release

Figure. No.7 First Order Kinetic Drug Release

Figure. No.8 Higuchi's Diffusion Plots

Figure. No.9 Koresmeyer-peppas Model

10. Kinetic studies data of F8 Formulation

The correlation coefficient r values of zero order of all the formulations were in the range of 0.9717 and first order r values were from 0.8183. The results suggest that, the drug was released by mixed order kinetics to ascertain, the drug release mechanism of the *in-vitro* release data for F8 formulation were calculated the kinetic studies in the Table. No.8. The Higuchi's diffusion plots and Peppas plots correlation coefficient values were in the range of 0.9413 and 0.9843 respectively in the Table.No.9 and Figure.No.6 to 9. So it confirms that, the calculated r values for Higuchi plot and Peppas plots were nearer to one (1) in all the cases suggesting that drug released by diffusion mechanism.

11. Stability studies of F8 Formulation

The optimized formulation F8 was charged on accelerated stability and monitored for physicochemical and drug release study at 1, 2 and 3 month. The stability study reveals no significant variation in physicochemical parameter and *in-vitro* release study up to 3 months. Stability studies for F8 formulation at different temperature were shown in the Table.No.10

REFERENCES:

1. Girish Chopda. Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems: A Review Pharmainfo.Net. 2006; 1(4): 31.
2. Hypertension: Wikipedia, the Free Encyclopedia (An U.S Registered 501 (3) Tax_Deductible Nonprofit Charity). Oct 2008.
3. Langer R. Transdermal Drug Delivery: Past Progress, Current Status, And Future Prospects. Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews. 2004; 56(5): 557-558.

4. Chein YW. Controlled and Novel Drug Delivery Systems. Newyork- Marcel Dekker. inc., 2nd ed. 1987; 524-552.
5. Chandrasekhar N.S, Shobha Rani R.H. Physicochemical and Pharmacokinetic Parameter in Drug Selection and Loading for Transdermal Delivery. Indian J.Pharm Sci. 2008; 70(1): 94-96.
6. Jamkandi V G, Mulla J S, Vinay B L, Shivakumar H N. Formulation, Characterization and Evaluation of Matrix Type Transdermal Patches of a Model Antihypertensive Drug. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutics. 2009.
7. Vijayan V. Development and Physiochemical, *In-Vitro* Evaluation of Antihypertensive Transdermal Patches. J. Pharm. Sci. & Res. 2010; 2(3): 171-177.
8. Panner Selvam R, Anoop Kumar Singh, Sivakumar T. Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems for Antihypertensive Drugs. Int J Pharm Biomed Res. 2010; 1(1): 1-8.
9. Misra AN, Jain N.K. Controlled and Novel Drug Delivery: Transdermal Drug Delivery. 1997; 100-101.
10. Keith AD. Polymer Matrix Consideration for Transdermal Devices. Drug Dev Ind. 1983; 9: 605-621.
11. Kulkarni R, Doddayya H, Marihal SC, Patil CC, Habbu PV. Comparative Evaluation of Polymeric Films for Transdermal Application. The Eastern Pharmacist. 2000; 43(516):109-112.
12. Aulton M.E. Pharmaceutics- The Science of Dosage from Design. 2nd ed. 90.
13. Vijaya R., **Ruckmani K.** In Vitro and In Vivo Characterization of the Transdermal Delivery of Sertraline Hydrochloride Films, **DARU Nov. 2011; (19).**

